

KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PERCEPTION ABOUT TEETHING AND ITS MANAGEMENT AMONG DENTAL INTERNS

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ORIGINAL RESEARCH

ABSTRACT

The process of teething in a child draws significant attention and interest for the paediatric dentist, the anxious parent and the paediatrician. A myriad of symptoms is presented by the child during the teething period. However, managing, guiding and advising the parents regarding teething requires an awareness and knowledge that should be instilled within the dental practitioner as early as possible. This short communication follows a Knowledge, Attitude and Practice/Perception Model which helps in deciphering the present knowledge of dental interns with respect to teething.

Keywords: Teething, Infant Oral Health, KAP

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INTRODUCTION

A teething period is defined as the period from four days before to three days after a tooth erupts.¹ In this 8-day window a child presents with a range of symptoms.² According to the American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry (AAPD), teething can lead to intermittent localized discomfort, irritability, low-grade fever and excessive salivation.³ Knowledge about the guidelines pertaining to teething and its management among pediatric dentists has been reported to be lacking or conflicting.⁴

METHOD

A customized online questionnaire (validated by subject experts after an initial trial survey) was designed based on the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice/Perception Model.⁵ An opening body of the survey included an explanation regarding why the survey is conducted and complete confidentiality regarding the participants' details. The survey was directed towards final year dental interns.

Questionnaire of the survey was divided into two categories: 7 questions pertaining to the basic knowledge of teething and 13 questions pertaining to its management. All ambiguities in the trial survey were removed before the final version was sent to participants via electronic means in November 2022. A snowball sampling technique was executed wherein included participants were from three different dental colleges. Data management was done using Google Forms and Microsoft Excel.

RESULTS

Only unique visitors were considered in the final sample. A response rate of 94.70% was determined following the exclusion of invalid and incomplete form submissions.

CONCLUSION

Teething or dentition difficilis is a condition which requires extensive awareness among dental students. Our survey results depict that teething requires more emphasis at an academic level for dentists to better guide the parents and guardians in the future.

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RECOMMENDED READING

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